

CLINICAL AUDIT : AN ELDERLY WOMAN WITH CELLULITIS, SUBCUTANEOUS ABSCESSSES, PERSISTENT FEVER AND POLYARTHRITIS

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Case Report

A 73-year-old woman was admitted on 30.11.1992 to the surgical department of the Princess Margaret Hospital via the accident and emergency department with the provisional diagnosis of carcinoma of breast. The patient had been unwell for one month prior to admission, complaining of feverishness, weight loss and progressively painful, hot right chest and right upper abdominal wall. There was no history of recent trauma. She had consulted many general practitioners and was given multiple medications: non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (mefenamic acid, naproxin), prednisolone, analgesics (gosalgesle), and antacids (stomacaine). The last general practitioner was seen on 27.11.1992 and she was treated as abscess and cellulitis with antibiotics (lincomycin, ampicillin, cloxacillin, ciprofloxacin, cefuroxime), and was also given mefenamic acid (ponstan), cimetidine, and antacids.

As for the past medical history, she was being followed up at another hospital for hypertension, hyperuricaemia, renal impairment and rheumatoid arthritis and was maintained on metoprolol and allopurinol. She had no history of diabetes or tuberculosis, nor did she have any history of chronic cough. She had history of traffic accident 2 years ago with fractured right clavicle. She was living with her family members, and her premorbid mobility and activities of daily living were independent.

In the surgical ward, her right chest wall and right flank was noted to be swollen, tender with cellulitis, induration and blister formation. She was running a swinging fever with a maximum temperature of 40°C. There was no lymphadenopathy. On admission, she was anaemic (Hb 8.4g/dl, normochromic normocytic), with neutrophilia (WCC $13.6 \times 10^9/l$, N90.4% L3.6%) and a high ESR of 138mm/hr. The liver and renal function tests were impaired (albumin 27g/l, globulin 24g/l, bilirubin 5µmol/l, alkaline phosphatase 124iu/l, alanine aminotransferase 48iu/l, sodium 136mmol/l, potassium 5.5mmol/l, urea 17.8mmol/l, creatinine 301µmol/l, urate 0.69 mmol/l, calcium 2.45mmol/l, phosphate 1.52mmol/l). The blood glucose was 6.2mmol/l. Cultures taken from blood and blister fluid were negative for organisms.

During the 3 week stay in the surgical ward, she had been given multiple antibiotics: ampicillin, cloxacillin, cephradine, ofloxacin, penicillin, metronidazole and cefuroxime; but the fever persisted with marked induration and inflammation over right flank and newly developed induration over left thigh with ulceration and purulent dis-

charge. Dermatologist's opinion was cellulitis and a skin biopsy was done, and the result later came back as mild non-specific acute on chronic inflammation without evidence of vasculitis. On the fourth day after admission, she complained of cough with yellowish sputum and was noted to be short of breath on several occasions. Chest examination revealed bilateral coarse crepitations. Repeat chest X-ray (Figure 1) taken two weeks after admission showed pneumonia and she was given in addition to antibiotics, oxygen, acetylcysteine and mid-expectorant stimulant (MES).

Figure 1. Chest X-ray 2 weeks after admission (portable AP film).

Computerised tomography (CT) thorax and abdomen done on 9.12.1992 showed probable inflammatory change in right chest and abdominal wall (Figure 2). The detailed report was "there is diffuse thickening of the chest and abdominal wall on the right side, with increased density and presence of soft tissue strands in the subcutaneous layer. The right pectoralis muscles are enlarged with fluffy outlines. The same applies to the abdominal wall muscles and fluid seems to interpose between the muscle layers. Overlying skin is thickened and enhanced. There is no obvious abscess collection or air pockets. Involvement from the level of axilla down to beyond the level of iliac crest is noted. Bilateral pleural effusion and left upper lobe collapse

Figure 2. CT thorax showing right subcutaneous inflammation.

Figure 3. CT thorax showing left upper lobe collapse consolidation with a speckle of calcium.

consolidation (Figure 3) are present. The liver, spleen, pancreas and kidneys are normal without any abdominal lymphadenopathy or ascites."

Her illness was complicated by upper gastrointestinal bleeding one week after admission, with Hb dropping to 5.3g/dl for which she had been transfused 4 pints of blood. The platelet count, prothrombin and partial thromboplastin times were normal. Oesophago-gastro-duodenoscopy (OGD) revealed chronic duodenal ulcer, and she was given ranitidine. She also had fresh vaginal bleeding two weeks after admission. Gynaecological assessment revealed that the patient had history of vaginal bleeding for the past 20 years, but no abnormality was detected on vaginal examination nor with pelvic ultrasonogram.

Two and a half weeks after admission, she complained of pain over right elbow and left ankle. Piroxicam was given with some improvement. Urate level was 0.66 mmol/l. Anti-nuclear antibody (ANA) was positive 1 in 360, centromere pattern while the rheumatoid factor was negative and the complement levels were normal. Underlying autoimmune disorder was suspected and she was taken over to the geriatric ward for further management on 22.12.1992.

On transfer, she was noted to have generalized oedema with erythematous induration over right chest wall and right loin, and ulceration with necrotic tissue over left thigh. She was afebrile, Hb 9.1g/dl, WCC $8.3 \times 10^9/l$ (N78.9%, L9.2%), ESR 80mm/hr, albumin 23g/l, globulin 24g/l, alkaline phosphatase 132iu/l, bilirubin 7umol/l, sodium 143 mmol/l, potassium 3.5mmol/l, urea 11.4mmol/l, creatinine 141umol/l, calcium 2.13mmol/l, phosphate 0.94mmol/l. Repeat anti-nuclear antibody and rheumatoid factor were negative. Anti-DNA, anti-ENA (Ro, La) were negative and the immunoglobulin pattern was normal. Antibody to HIV was negative. High protein diet and low dose frusemide were given to relieve the generalized oedema. All the antibiotics were stopped and cultures were repeated from blood, spu-

tum, mid-stream urine and wound swab.

Five blood cultures were repeated: four were negative while the last one grew Gram-negative *Alcaligenes* species. *Candida albicans* was cultured from the sputum (heavy growth), mid-stream urine and wound swab. Sputum culture also showed moderate growth of *Klebsiella* species (sensitive to cefuroxime). Right loin tissue grew no fungi nor actinomycetes, but showed scanty growth of *Streptococcus sanguis* I while direct smear showed no acid-fast bacilli (AFB). Left thigh wound swab grew *Acinetobacter* species (heavy growth) and methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (heavy growth), but showed no AFB on smear.

Fever kicked up again one day after stopping the antibiotics, with a maximum temperature of 38.5°C. Six days later, she developed acute arthritis over both knees, right middle finger and right elbow. She was thus started on indomethacin suppository and the fever subsided two days afterwards with improvement of the arthritis. However the left thigh wound and right chest wall deteriorated with abscess formation (fluctuant). Debridement of the necrotic skin over the anterior aspect of left thigh and removal of blood-stained exudate were done by an orthopaedic surgeon on 2.1.93 while incision and drainage of right chest wall abscess were done by a surgeon on 7.1.93. The right chest wall tissue was sent for bacterial culture, AFB smear and culture, and for histology. The patient continued to deteriorate with hypercalcaemia (serum calcium 3.18mmol/l, phosphate 1.49mmol/l, albumin 25g/l) and the clinical picture of acute pancreatitis (diffuse abdominal pain with tenderness, rebound and guarding, serum amylase 1517iu/l). She was treated conservatively with parenteral fluid hydration, frusemide, hydrocortisone, nasogastric suction, cefuroxime and metronidazole. On 9.1.1993, the sputum for AFB smear result came back as positive. Active pulmonary tuberculosis was diagnosed. Hydrocortisone was stopped and she was started on anti-tuberculosis drugs

(isoniazid, rifampicin and pyrazinamide). She continued to deteriorate with hypocalcaemia (serum calcium 1.18mmol/l, phosphate 2.94mmol/l, albumin 21g/l) and worsening of renal function (urea 25.3mmol/l, creatinine 362umol/l). She finally succumbed on 12.1.1993.

After her death, direct smears for AFB in the left thigh necrotic tissue and right chest wall necrotic tissue came back as positive. The biopsy of the right chest wall abscess (taken on 7.1.1993) was reported as "extensive inflammatory cellular infiltrate in the fibrofatty tissue, with large areas of necrosis. The infiltrate consists of a mixture of neutrophils, plasma cells, lymphocytes, and, in some foci, collection of epithelioid histiocytes and multinucleated giant cells (Figure 4). Ziehl-Neelsen stain shows numerous acid-fast bacilli consistent with mycobacterial infection (Figure 5)." Bone marrow smear for AFB and culture for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* were negative. Two specimens of urine for AFB smear and culture were negative. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was cultured from the second sputum specimen, the left thigh wound swab and necrotic tissue, and right chest wall necrotic tissue. Her family members strongly refused post-mortem examination.

Figure 4. Low power photomicrograph of right chest wall abscess biopsy showing extensive inflammatory infiltration in the abscess wall, associated with areas of necrosis. Note multinucleated giant cell (arrowhead).

Figure 5. Ziehl-Neelsen stain of right chest wall abscess revealing numerous acid-fast bacilli (arrowheads).

Discussion

I use a very special instrument called a retrospectroscope to look back and review the whole case record to see why the diagnosis of tuberculosis has been delayed in this patient.

In a study of the diagnosis of tuberculosis in a general hospital, Stack¹ found that the diagnostic delay after hospital admission was 10.9 days when tuberculosis was included in the initial diagnosis, but the delay was prolonged to 22.8 days when tuberculosis was not included in the initial differential diagnosis. Tuberculosis was not initially suspected in this patient and it was only diagnosed 41 days after admission. The main reasons for failed or delayed diagnosis as mentioned by various authors^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8} are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Reasons for failed or delayed diagnosis of tuberculosis in the elderly patient

lack of respiratory symptoms
disease/ drugs depressing the immune system:
corticosteroids, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
concomitant disease masking the clinical picture of tuberculosis
willingness to accept the diagnosis of a generalized malignancy with no histological evidence
possibility of reactivation of a dormant infection was not thought of, despite tuberculosis had been diagnosed in past health (old tuberculosis)
unusual extrapulmonary manifestations
"atypical" radiological findings of chest X-ray
solitary nodules
mass-like densities
extensive bronchopneumonia
lower lobe infiltrates
apical scarring/ apical pleural thickening initially thought to represent only old or stable tuberculosis
(33% of tuberculosis diagnosed only at autopsy have chest X-ray reports of old tuberculosis)

The **drug history** is of particular importance in dealing with elderly patients. Polypharmacy and inappropriate prescription in the aged have resulted in unnecessary poisoning⁹. The most recent medication of this patient was mentioned in the referral letter of the referring general practitioner. However, the patient had been put on multiple medications by other general practitioners. Some of those medications had been sent for identification by pharmacists but none could be identified. In the case record was a small piece of paper showing that she had been on prednisolone, mefanamic acid (ponstan), naproxin (synproten) and an analgesic (gosalglesle). No information was obtained why and how long the patient had been put on prednisolone. Corticosteroids not only facilitate the development of tuberculosis by adversely affecting the host's defenses against tubercle bacilli¹⁰ but may also suppress the clinical manifes-

tations, thus delaying diagnosis until a later stage^{1,7}. Prolonged steroid treatment accounted for 20.7% of undiagnosed tuberculosis in one autopsy study⁵. The patient had been put on 4-quinolones (ciprofloxacin) before admission. Since 4-quinolones¹¹ have anti-tuberculosis activity, such unintended partial treatment may also modify the fever response, making diagnosis more difficult. She had been put on non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID) before admission (mefenamic acid, naproxen). Both steroids and NSAID can precipitate upper gastro-intestinal bleeding, which did occur in this patient after admission. More importantly, NSAID have been reported¹² and shown¹³ to activate tuberculosis and also mask infections.

The main focus was on her skin problem throughout her hospital stay. **Respiratory** symptom was not the patient's chief complaint. On admission, it was recorded that the patient had no cough or sputum. Nevertheless, the patient did complain of cough with sputum 4 days after admission and was noted to have shortness of breath on several occasions. Chest crepitations were noted on examination, but a study by Connolly¹⁴ et al. revealed that crepitations in acute elderly patients are neither sensitive nor specific. Tachypnoea is a more useful sign in the elderly patient and precedes clinical diagnosis of respiratory infection by 3 to 4 days. However, there was no mention of the respiratory rate on chest examination. Based on the chest X-ray finding two weeks after admission (Figure 1), she was thought to have pneumonia. Of the many chest X-ray films, only the one taken at the accident and emergency department was an erect PA film (Figure 6), which was unreported. The film was retrospectively reviewed by a radiologist, who noted soft tissue shadow over the apex of left lung, thickened right horizontal fissure, elevated right

Figure 6. Chest X-ray on admission (PA film) showing soft tissue shadow over the apex of left lung.

hemi-diaphragm and old fracture of right clavicle, but no evidence of active tuberculosis. The CT scan of thorax was taken to examine the chest wall lesion. As a "by-product", it also showed "collapse-consolidation of left upper lobe (Figure 3), bilateral pleural effusion". Sputum for AFB was ordered on 7.12.1992 and 23.12.1992 as part of the sepsis "screen." However, the first sputum specimen was obtained only on 15.12.1992 and was later reported as negative for AFB on smear and culture. The second sputum sample, taken on 23.12.1992 was reported on 6.1.1993 to be positive for AFB, but this positive result reached the ward on 9.1.1993 only. Certainly there was delay in obtaining the sputum specimen, sending it to a distant off-site (15km away) laboratory centralized for AFB examination, examining the specimen and sending the result back to the ward. The delay between collection and report (14 days) might be due to delay in transport from the ward to the centralized laboratory and closure of laboratory and transport services during the Christmas and New Year holidays. The delay between the report and notification of result to the ward (3 days) might be due to delay in sending the report from the laboratory to the hospital and then back to the ward.

Apical lesions without cavitations are frequently thought to represent only old or inactive tuberculosis. Cavitations are not that common in elderly patients with active pulmonary tuberculosis¹⁵. In one study¹⁶, 10-12% of patients with active pulmonary tuberculosis had apical scarring or apical pleural thickening initially thought to represent only old tuberculosis. Apical lesions should be viewed as dormant tuberculosis foci capable of reactivation at any time. Clinical correlation is therefore important. In this patient previously on steroids, with productive cough and dyspnoea and persistent fever and high ESR, such apical lesions would suggest reactivated tuberculosis foci. Had tuberculosis been seriously thought of initially, the clinician would definitely ensure early collection of sputum sample and collaborate with the laboratory staff for an urgent examination for AFB. Studies in Hong Kong have shown that acute tuberculous pneumonia is an important cause of pneumonia locally, both in the community-acquired group¹⁷ and the non-HIV infected immunocompromised patients¹⁸. These studies also found that tuberculous pneumonia could not be differentiated readily from other causes of pneumonia on clinical and radiological grounds, although pleural effusion and upper lobe involvement were more common in patients with tuberculosis. Thus tuberculosis should be considered in patients who fail to respond to first-line antibiotics.

The **skin** problem was the patient's major complaint: progressive painful hot right chest and right upper abdominal wall for one month. It had been variously labeled as carcinoma of breast, abscess, cellulitis, and vasculitis. The diagnosis of cellulitis was favoured by dermatologist. CT thorax and abdomen in the early stage showed only probable inflammatory change in right chest and abdominal wall (mainly subcutaneous) with thickened overlying skin,

Figure 8. Temperature chart 20.12.1992 - 11.1.1993. Note evening fever pattern when antibiotics stopped, and the decline in fever with indomethacin.

results. After being taken over to the geriatric ward, the decision was made to stop all antibiotics and repeat the sepsis workup. When all the antibiotics were stopped, observation of the fever pattern (Figure 8) showed a predominant evening fever, which is said to be characteristic of tuberculosis and may be missed unless rectal temperature is measured in the late afternoon or evening²⁵. The fever pattern had been modified in this patient by ice-packs, antibiotics and NSAID. Indomethacin was started for polyarthrititis and possible underlying autoimmune disease. Besides masking the fever response (Figure 8), indomethacin might actually activate and spread the tuberculosis infection as mentioned earlier on^{12,13}. To emphasize this point, I report briefly another elderly patient with tuberculosis meningitis after indomethacin in the appendix.

In the elderly patient, we tend to accept multiple pathology. However, in this patient, one might ask can tuberculosis explain all her problems and what is the **extent of tuberculosis involvement** in her. Late generalized tuberculosis has evolved from a disease affecting young adults to one afflicting the elderly people²⁶, and it is in this older population that extrapulmonary tuberculosis foci in concealed sites and asymptomatic generalized tuberculosis frequently occurs. Tuberculosis of skin and lungs were confirmed in this patient by histology and culture. The twenty years of **postmenopausal bleeding** up to the time of hospitalization might as well be due to genital tuberculosis. There have been case reports of skeletal tuberculosis diagnosed up to 24 years after hysterectomy with the initial genital involvement missed²⁷. The **renal impairment** might be part of the genito-urinary tuberculosis with secondary hypertension and hyperuricaemia. The follow-up history and workup of this patient in another hospital were not available for review.

She had been labeled as **rheumatoid arthritis**. How-

ever, the rheumatoid factor was negative and there was no radiological evidence of rheumatoid arthritis from X-ray of her hands. There have been case reports of tuberculosis arthritis misdiagnosed as rheumatoid arthritis²⁷ and tuberculous arthritis presenting as tophaceous gout²⁸. Besides direct tuberculous infection of joints, there is another entity known as **tuberculous rheumatism** (Poncet's disease) first described by Poncet 100 years ago. He observed polyarthrititis or diffuse arthralgia in patients with tuberculosis, notable for the absence of mycobacteria in involved joints. Although the existence of Poncet's disease had been questioned²⁹, there have been case reports^{30,31,32} of tuberculous rheumatism with resolution of symptoms after anti-tuberculous therapy. Tuberculous rheumatism is said to be more common in people of Asian, African and Caribbean origin²⁵. Could this patient had tuberculous rheumatism? Distinction of tuberculous rheumatism from rheumatoid arthritis is important because symptomatic treatment with NSAID or steroids would activate tuberculosis and also mask its diagnosis. Patients with tuberculous rheumatism might present as myalgia and arthralgia³⁰ and might be mistaken as polymyalgia rheumatica and given steroids. Rheumatic complaints, worse in coldness and air-conditioning settings, are common among our local Chinese elderly people. In how many of them have tuberculosis been suspected? Or are they just treated symptomatically with steroids and NSAID?

The positive ANA result was interpreted with too much weight in this patient. Autoimmune disease was suspected because of this result, coupled with polyarthrititis, unexplained fever and the skin lesion. However, skin biopsy revealed no evidence of vasculitis and the repeat ANA was negative. Such autoantibodies are not uncommon in the elderly patients and may just be noise confusing the diagnosis. Anticardiolipin antibodies have been reported in ischaemic strokes in elderly patients without systemic lupus erythematosus³³, and also in ischaemic heart disease and in tuberculosis³⁴. Nevertheless, autoantibodies and immune complexes as well as other autoimmune events are frequent in tuberculosis and the relationship between mycobacteria and human autoimmune disease is the subject of intense study³⁵. It has been proposed that some autoimmune disease (e.g. reactive arthritis) may be mediated through "molecular mimicry" between mycobacterial stress protein antigens and their human homologs³⁶. Cross-reactivity between mycobacterial glycolipids and nuclear antigens has also been demonstrated³⁷. However, diversion of a clinician to such autoimmune phenomena may delay the diagnosis of the underlying tuberculosis infection.

The cause of **upper gastro-intestinal bleeding** seemed obvious in this patient: she had been put on steroids and NSAID and OGD revealed chronic duodenal ulcer. However, tuberculous duodenal ulceration was recognised long before peptic ulceration³⁸. Some elderly patients swallowed their sputum instead of coughing it out. Whether this patient had tuberculous duodenal ulceration was not known because it is not a usual practice to biopsy

the duodenum and send a specimen for AFB during OGD. Perhaps, nobody would ever think of tuberculous duodenal ulceration nowadays.

Various authors^{5,15,39,40} have suggested that **raised alkaline phosphatase and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)** are associated with extrapulmonary tuberculosis. The highest alkaline phosphatase and LDH in this patient were 132iu/l and 1645iu/l respectively. The serum albumin was low (27g/l) on admission and it dropped to 21g/l just before death. Whether **hypoalbuminaemia** is a reflection of active disease or a marker of pre-existing malnutrition predisposing towards the disease is not known¹⁵. She had normochromic normocytic anaemia. A bone marrow biopsy was done but there was insufficient material for examination; the marrow smear was negative for AFB.

Initially the cause for the **hypercalcaemia** was unclear and later it was attributed to tuberculosis when the sputum result for AFB returned as positive. Hypercalcaemia in tuberculosis is thought to be related to extrarenal synthesis of 1,25(OH)2D3^{41,42,43}. The hypercalcaemia of other granulomatous disease like sarcoid is responsive to steroids. Hydrocortisone, initially started for hypercalcaemia, was stopped when tuberculosis was diagnosed. The role of steroids in tuberculosis has been under debate and some would⁴⁴ recommend trying corticosteroids in patients in whom systemic symptoms or local pressure effects are a problem, provided that the patient is taking antituberculous drugs to which the organisms are sensitive. Subsequently the patient developed acute pancreatitis, which could be due to hypercalcaemia, frusemide, or penetration/perforation of duodenal ulcer. She had the poor prognostic factors of pancreatitis (hypocalcaemia, hypoalbuminaemia, hypoxaemia, azotaemia) and finally succumbed with multi-organ failure. One study⁴⁵ has revealed that 1 in 8 elderly patients died before anti-tuberculosis treatment was completed, emphasizing that treatment must be given as early as possible if the elderly patient is to recover.

The crucial point in diagnosing tuberculosis is a **high index of suspicion**⁴⁶. With the decline in tuberculosis, there is concern over decrease in diagnostic and management skills of tuberculosis^{4,5,47,48}. Tuberculosis has been recognised as increasingly a disease of the elderly people^{47,48,49}. The remark made by Sir William Osler 100 years ago still holds true today:

"It is remarkable how common tuberculosis is in the aged, particularly in institutions."

William Osler 1892

Today the majority of tuberculosis cases in developed countries occur in persons who were infected in earlier decades, i.e., aged 65 and older^{49,50}. Many survived the initial infection but continued to harbour bacilli in dormant caseous and even calcified lesions. Reactivation of such dormant lesions may occur in those elderly persons with predisposing factors, including diabetes mellitus, malnutrition, long-term corticosteroid therapy, alcohol abuse, smok-

Figure 9. Age-specific case rates of tuberculosis per 100,000 population in Hong Kong for the years 1981, 1986, 1991.

ing, other debilitating diseases, and nursing home residence^{49,50,51,52,53}. Studies by Stead et al.⁵¹ also suggested that many previously infected persons have outlived their initial infecting organism and become vulnerable to exogenous reinfection with tuberculosis and may subsequently have the disease. Data from Stead et al.⁵⁴ in the United States (US) between 1961 and 1981 showed that there was an actual increase in the age-specific rate of tuberculosis for those aged over 80 though there is decline in tuberculosis for other age groups. The same is true for the elderly population in Hong Kong. The age-specific case rate of tuberculosis in Hong Kong for 1981, 1986, and 1991 (Figure 9) is derived using data obtained from the Hong Kong Chest Service, and the Hong Kong Census and Statistics Department. It can be seen from Figure 9 that there is a decline in the age-specific case rate of tuberculosis from the year 1981 to 1991 for all age groups except those aged over 70, and the **age-specific tuberculosis case rate is the highest for those aged over 70**, amounting to 301 cases per 100,000 population in the year 1991. In the US during 1986 to 1988, 27% to 28% of tuberculosis cases occurred in persons aged 65 or older, who then constituted 12% of the US population⁵⁰. In Hong Kong from 1981 to 1991 (Figure 10), the 65+ elderly population has risen from 6.55% to 8.72%, yet the 65+ elderly tuberculosis cases have accelerated from 13.1% to 22.2%. The actual size of the problem of tuberculosis in the aged might be even greater because the case rate might be under-estimated due to under-diagnosis and under-notification⁵⁵. One epidemiological study⁵⁶ in Italy has shown that the total tuberculosis case rate based on anti-tuberculosis drug prescriptions is seven times that of the official notification. Hospital doctors seldom notify tuberculosis, whether diagnosed during life or post-mortem. Notification is important not only for accurate morbidity statistics, but also for contact tracing and case finding. As tuberculosis is a communicable disease, nobody is safe until everybody is safe.

Conclusions

1. Active tuberculosis is highly prevalent in the aged popu-

Figure 10. Increase in percentage of tuberculosis cases in elderly persons (aged 65+) compared to increase in elderly population for the years 1981, 1986, 1991 in Hong Kong.

lation.

- The clinical features of tuberculosis in the aged person may be atypical, nonspecific, or confused with coexisting diseases.
- Correct diagnosis of tuberculosis by the clinician depends on a high index of suspicion of the disease.
- Tuberculosis must always be included in the initial differential diagnosis of unexplained illness in the elderly patients, especially when associated with depression of the immune system, including various malignancies, prolonged therapy with steroids, NSAID and cytotoxic drugs.
- The failure to diminish the pyrexia believed due to specific infections with presumably effective antibiotics, and the inability of therapy to control other conditions thought to cause the fever, indicate the presence of tuberculosis.
- Diagnostic delay can be reduced by early collection of specimens or biopsies to demonstrate either the organisms or characteristic histological changes. Initial negative sputum smears do not rule out the diagnosis. Multiple examinations need to be carried out.
- Appropriate interpretation of radiographic and clinical information minimize delay in diagnosis. It is important to recognize the full spectrum of radiological manifestations of pulmonary tuberculosis as outlined in Table 1.
- The importance of diagnosis is that the disease is curable if diagnosed, but fatal if undiagnosed. An undiagnosed infective person is of epidemiologic importance, being a hazard to both the community and hospital staff.
- If the diagnosis of tuberculosis is highly suggestive, even without bacteriologic confirmation, a therapeutic trial of antituberculosis drugs should be given, since this lethal disease may then be cured before it progresses to the irreversible state.

Appendix: Tuberculous meningitis after indomethacin

A 80-year-old man was admitted into the surgical ward on 20.8.1991 for head injury after a fall while getting off from bed. He had similar history of fall with minor head

injury in May 1991 and was then treated at the Accident and Emergency Department without hospitalization. He sustained a laceration over the right eyebrow and was conscious and alert throughout. Neurological observation was stable. An evening fever (Figure 11) occurred after admission and he had cough with whitish sputum. Cefuroxime was started on 24.8.1991. Indomethacin was also started on 26.8.1991 for left knee pain and right foot pain. The fever subsided on 27.8.1991. Chest X-ray revealed a coin lesion over right middle zone and he was subsequently transferred to a chest hospital for observation on 10.9.1991. He was readmitted to the geriatric ward on 14.9.1991 from the chest hospital because of disorientation, neck rigidity, tremor and fever. Tuberculous meningitis was subsequently diagnosed and his condition improved after anti-tuberculous treatment. Review of the hospital record showed that he had been put on indomethacin at a dose of 25mg four times a day from 26.8.1991 till 10.9.1991.

Figure 11. Temperature chart 20.8.1991 - 8.9.1991 for appendix.

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